

Identification and functional characterization of CYP3002B2, a cytochrome P450 associated with amitraz and flumethrin resistance in the major bee parasite *Varroa destructor*

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ABSTRACT

Beekeeping worldwide is increasingly threatened by the parasitic mite *Varroa destructor*, whose management relies heavily on synthetic acaricides such as amitraz and flumethrin. However, the growing incidence of acaricide resistance in *V. destructor* presents a significant global challenge to apiculture. In this study, we investigated the mechanisms underlying resistance to these compounds in a *V. destructor* population exhibiting reduced susceptibility to both amitraz and flumethrin. Specifically, bioassays revealed that the resistant population (IL-R) displayed 35.0 % mortality in response to amitraz and 39.5 % mortality to flumethrin, in contrast to >90 % mortality observed in the susceptible IL-L and ATH-S populations. The resistance phenotype was not strongly associated with any of the known target site mutations; the putative amitraz resistance mutation F290L in the *Octβ2R* gene, and the pyrethroid resistant mutation L925V in the *vgsc* gene, were found at low frequencies (8.6 % and 13.6 % respectively). Transcriptomic analysis, comparing gene expression levels between the resistant population and two susceptible populations, revealed that resistance is associated with the overexpression of several cuticle genes and the cytochrome P450 gene *CYP3002B2*. *CYP3002B2* was functionally expressed in *E. coli*, exhibiting catalytic activity against multiple model substrates and effectively metabolizing both amitraz and flumethrin. The predominant product of amitraz metabolism is likely an inactive, hydroxylated form of the insecticide, rather than any of the known activated/toxic metabolites of amitraz. These findings are crucial for evidence-based *V. destructor* management, as *CYP3002B2* is the first detoxification enzyme shown to metabolize two major acaricides from different modes of action classes.

1. Introduction

Beekeeping is an essential part of agriculture, contributing significantly to global food, economic, and ecological securities (Hung et al., 2018; Papa et al., 2022). The direct economic contributions of beekeeping include the production of honey, beeswax, royal jelly, and other valuable products. Indirectly, honeybees are essential to agriculture and global food production given that they act as key pollinators of most insect-dependent crops (Gallai et al., 2009; Khalifa et al., 2021). Since 2006, however, colony collapse has significantly increased across North America and most European countries, leading to substantial economic losses and harmful downstream effects on both agriculture

and apiculture. The major cause of colony collapses across these regions has been determined to be related to the proliferation of the honey bee parasitic mite *Varroa destructor* (*V. destructor*) (Hristov et al., 2020; Neumann and Carreck, 2010; Potts et al., 2010), making it one of the greatest threats to honeybee populations globally. The mite inflicts damage directly by feeding on the fat body tissue and hemolymph of the bees, and indirectly by vectoring viruses that further compromise bee health (Morfin et al., 2023; Ramsey et al., 2019). High infestations of *V. destructor* can lead to increased mortality rates, reduced brood areas, diminished honey yields, and ultimately the collapse of colonies within a few years if left unmanaged. Economic losses associated with *V. destructor* infestations already reach into the hundreds of billions of

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dollars (Warner et al., 2024), meaning effective pest management practices for the pest must be developed and employed to secure the future of apiculture and the wider agricultural markets.

Management of *V. destructor* has predominantly relied on the use of synthetic acaricides such as amitraz, pyrethroids (tau-fluvalinate and flumethrin) and the organophosphate coumaphos, as well as organic acids and thymol. Among them, amitraz, –a disruptor of the α - and β -adrenergic-like octopamine receptors (Oct β 2R) (IRAC group 19) (Kita et al., 2017; Ohta and Ozoe, 2014) – remains one of the most efficient and highly selective registered compounds in Europe and other regions (Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2021; Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2022), while flumethrin is also used in many geographical regions.

Amitraz is a pro-acaricide/insecticide; its action is dependent on both the toxicity of the parental compound, as well as the formation of metabolized active compounds such as N2-(2,4-dimethylphenyl)-N1-methyl formamide (DPMF), 2,4-dimethylformanilide (DMF), 2,4-dimethylaniline (DMA) which are formed inside the target organism by enzyme based activation mechanisms (Davenport et al., 1985). Among the active compounds amitraz is metabolized into, DPMF is a more potent agonist of the Oct β 2R receptor than the parent molecule, thereby enhancing its pesticidal efficacy (Cai et al., 2023; Kita et al., 2017; Takata et al., 2020). It acts as an agonist for octopamine receptors, particularly targeting the β -adrenergic-like octopamine receptor (β AOR, specifically Oct β 2R), which triggers hyperexcitation in pests. Flumethrin is a pyrethroid insecticide that acts at voltage-gated sodium channel (VGSC), disrupting their normal function by prolonging sodium influx, leading to hyperexcitation, paralysis, and eventual death in target pests (Soderlund and Bloomquist, 1989).

In recent years, the emergence of acaricide-resistant *V. destructor* populations have been described at an increasing level of incidence across the globe, including resistance to pyrethroids, amitraz and organophosphates (Almecija et al., 2022; Bahreini et al., 2025; González-Cabrera et al., 2016; Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2021; Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2022; Jack and Ellis, 2021; Millán-Leiva et al., 2021; Vlogiannitis et al., 2021a; Vlogiannitis et al., 2021b). Acaricide resistance mechanisms include reduced compound penetration, mutations in the target site of the pesticides, and detoxification or reduced activation of the pesticide by cytochrome P450s (CYPs) and other detoxification enzymes (De Rouck et al., 2023). Penetration resistance, also known as cuticular resistance, occurs in the initial phase of insecticide entry, where the insect or mite cuticle acts as the first defensive barrier. Alterations to the properties of the cuticle, often through a thickening of the chitin layers, has been found to correlate strongly to reduced pesticide penetration in target pest arthropods (Balabanidou et al., 2018). Such thickening of the cuticle slows down the penetration process, delaying pesticide binding to target proteins while simultaneously allowing detoxification enzymes more time to act, thus enhancing resistance. These alterations have been associated with cuticle genes or enzymes that change the composition of the cuticle (Balabanidou et al., 2018) and often confer cross-resistance across different chemical classes (Balabanidou et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2018).

Target site resistance has been associated with amino acid substitutions in the VGSC in the case of pyrethroids, and the Oct β 2R in the case of amitraz. Kdr-type resistance mostly involves mutations at position 925 of the *vgs* gene. To date, three resistant alleles have been identified at this site; L925V, L925I, and L925M (González-Cabrera et al., 2013; González-Cabrera et al., 2016). The L925V mutation has been reported in the European continent; namely in Central and Southern England (González-Cabrera et al., 2013), Italy (Panini et al., 2019), Greece (Alissandrakis et al., 2017), Czechia (Hubert et al., 2014; Stara et al., 2019) and Türkiye (Koc et al., 2021). The L925I mutation has been reported in the USA (González-Cabrera et al., 2013), Türkiye (Erdem et al., 2024; Koc et al., 2021) and Greece (Alissandrakis et al., 2017), and the L925M mutation has so far been detected in the USA (González-Cabrera et al., 2013), Türkiye (Erdem et al., 2024) and Japan (Ogihara et al., 2021). A further substitution, M918L, has been reported

in Spain in combination with the L925V mutation (Benito-Murcia et al., 2022). Other putative mutations—specifically L1596P, M1823I, F1528L, and I1752V—have been found in resistant mites from Michigan and Florida in the USA, however, the role of these mutations in resistance remains to be functionally validated (Dong et al., 2014; Rinkevich, 2020; Wang et al., 2002). Mutations N87S, Y215H, F290L and Y337F in Oct β 2R have also been suggested as being associated with amitraz resistance in *V. destructor* mites (Guo et al., 2021; Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2022; Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2024; Inak et al., 2024; Marsky et al., 2024; Rinkevich et al., 2023). Of these, the Y337F mutation has been functionally validated in vivo through CRISPR-Cas9 editing, demonstrating that it confers a threefold increase in resistance to amitraz (Inak et al., 2024). Additional research is required to further validate and measure the impact of the remaining mutations.

Metabolic resistance has been less frequently reported in *V. destructor*. CYP monooxygenases have been implicated amitraz resistance via bioassays involving synergists (Chevillon et al., 2007; de La Canal et al., 2021; Ducornez et al., 2005). There is, however, only one documented case of functionally characterized CYP-based acaricide resistance in *V. destructor*: Specifically, reduced levels of the CYP4EP4, which is involved in the activation of the pro-insecticide coumaphos to coumaphos-oxon, were shown to confer resistance to coumaphos (Vlogiannitis et al., 2021b). The role of detoxification in amitraz and pyrethroid resistance in *V. destructor* mites has yet to be characterized at the molecular or functional level.

In this study, we identified a population of *V. destructor* mites resistant to both amitraz and flumethrin and characterized the underlying resistance mechanism using transcriptomic analyses and functional approaches.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Pesticides and chemicals

All fluorescent substrates and products, including 7-hydroxy-4-trifluoromethyl coumarin (HFC; CAS: 575–03-1), 7-ethoxy-4-trifluoromethyl coumarin (EFC; CAS: 115453–82-2), 7-hydroxy-coumarin (HC; CAS: 93–35-6), 7-ethoxy-coumarin (EC; CAS: 31005–02–4), 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (HMC; CAS: 90–33-5), 7-ethoxy-4-methylcoumarin (EMC; CAS: 87–05-8), fluorescein (F; CAS: 153954), and dibenzyl fluorescein (DEF; CAS: 21934–70-3), along with other chemicals, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich/Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The structures of these fluorescent substrates and products are listed in Suppl. Table S1.

2.2. Mite populations

Varroa destructor populations were collected from two sites in Israel, Modiin (31°52'30"N 34°58'21"E) and Volcani (31°59'32"N 34°49'13"E) (henceforth referred to as IL-R and IL-L, respectively), where acaricides, including amitraz and flumethrin, have been used. The IL-R population had been subjected to intensive acaricide treatments, with observed reductions in their efficacy, whereas the IL-L population had remained untreated for at least a year prior to collection. A third *V. destructor* population, collected from beehives at the Agricultural University of Athens, Greece, was used as the susceptible strain. This bee colony has been maintained without chemical treatments for the last twenty years (henceforth named ATH–S).

2.3. Bioassays

Laboratory tests were conducted to assess the susceptibility of adult female *V. destructor* mites to amitraz and flumethrin in treated bioassay glass vials. Stock solutions of technical grade insecticides (>95 % purity, Sigma Aldrich) were prepared in acetone and stored at –20 °C. Dilutions were prepared in acetone, and 0.5 mL aliquots were added to individual

glass vials (Kimble, 60965D-3). The vials were dried for at least one day and stored with the lids off to avoid moisture build up, in the dark, at 25 °C. Vials for control treatments were prepared in a similar way using only the acetone diluent. The diagnostic doses to assess *V. destructor* resistance to acaricides were set at 20 mg/L (ppm) for amitraz and 1 mg/L (ppm) for flumethrin, i.e., the calculated LC99 of the susceptible populations ATH—S. Adult female *V. destructor* mites were collected after either uncapping bee brood cells, or through using established sugar dusting methods. Batches of 10 *V. destructor* mites were transferred into the coated vials and incubated at 25 °C, 60 % RH for 20 h. Dose-response bioassays were conducted for ATH—S, while four replicates of the diagnostic doses plus control samples were tested for each of the IL-R and IL-L populations. After the exposure period, the mites were prodded with a fine paintbrush and considered dead in the absence of movement. Toxicity data were analyzed using PoloPC (LeOra Software, Berkeley, CA, USA).

2.4. Molecular analyses of acaricide resistance mechanisms

Genomic DNA (gDNA) was extracted from a total of 129 individual mites across the three populations (IL-R; $N = 63$, IL-L, $N = 56$; ATH-S = 10) using DNAzol with slight modifications of the manufacturer protocol (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA); 200 μ L of DNAzol reagent was used for homogenization, followed by the addition of 100 μ L of absolute ethanol for DNA precipitation. The samples were air-dried for 15 min on a 50 °C heat block, and the DNA was solubilized in 10 μ L of DNase/RNase-free water. Samples were stored at -20 °C until PCR analysis.

TaqMan diagnostic assays on each individual sample were used to assess target site mutations. The N87S and Y215H mutations of the β 2-adrenergic-like octopamine receptor gene (*Oct β 2R*), which are linked to amitraz resistance, were assessed using the protocol described in (Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2022). The L925V, L925I, and L925M mutations of the *vpsc* gene, associated with pyrethroid resistance, were evaluated based on ((González-Cabrera et al., 2016). Additionally, sequencing results from the transcriptomic analyses were examined to screen for any previously unreported, non-synonymous target-site mutations in the *Oct β 2R* and *vpsc* genes (sample sizes: IL-R, $N = 15$; IL-L, $N = 10$).

2.5. Transcriptomic analysis

Total RNA was extracted from 5 individuals of each of the two populations from Israel, with three replicates from IL-R and two from IL-L. RNA extraction was performed using the TRI reagent protocol (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) according to manufacturer instructions, and the samples were treated with TURBO DNase I (ThermoFisher Scientific) to eliminate genomic DNA contamination. Illumina RNA sequencing was performed to assess the transcriptome using the protocol described in (Vlogiannitis et al., 2021b). Illumina RNAseq reads for the susceptible *V. destructor* population from Athens (ATH—S), were downloaded from Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO), accession no. GSE153472. Raw RNAseq reads from the three *V. destructor* populations were quality-assessed using FASTQC (Andrews, 2010) and trimmed using Trimmomatic (Bolger et al., 2014). Trimmed reads were subsequently mapped onto the reference *V. destructor* genome using STARv2.7.10b (Dobin et al., 2013) and expression was quantified at the gene level using featureCounts (Liao et al., 2014). Next, normalized expression values (Transcripts Per Million - TPM) were computed using a custom Perl script and were utilized for performing a Principal Component Analysis (PCA). PCA visualization was achieved with ggplot2 and ggfortify (Tang et al., 2016). The differential expression (DE) analysis was carried out using edgeR (Robinson et al., 2010) with the following parameters: $\log_2|FC| > 1$, p -value $< 1E-3$, FDR < 0.05 . Boxplot was visualized using ggplot2 (Villanueva and Chen, 2019). Variant Calling was performed using BCFtools 1.204, with default parameters (Danecek et al., 2021).

2.6. Cloning, co-expression of CYP with CPR and preparation of membranes

The CYP and CPR sequences from were optimized for bacterial codon usage utilizing the Thermo Fisher Gene Optimizer tool (USA). The CYP coding sequences were synthesized by Azenta (Germany) and subcloned into the pCW-OmpA2 vector using the primers GCCGGCATGTTT-GAACTGGTCTGTCTTCT and GAGCTCTTACTGGGTAACACGACGC; underlined sections of the primer sequences correspond to recognition sites of the restriction enzymes NgoMIV and SacI, respectively, used for the subcloning step. The CPR sequence was synthesized and provided in the pCDFDuet-1 vector (Twist, UK).

Co-expression of the *V. destructor* CYP with *Tetranychus urticae* (*T. urticae*) CPR in the BL21 (DE3) Star *E. coli* strain (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) was performed according to (Riga et al., 2015). *T. urticae* CPR was selected due to its availability and its established use in enhancing P450 catalytic activity in mites. Briefly, transformed cells were grown in the presence of antibiotics in rich medium. At an optical density of ~ 0.8 – 0.9 cm^{-1} at 600 nm, 0.5 mM isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside and 1 mM heme precursor δ -aminolaevulinic acid were added, and the culture was further incubated at 25 °C for 24 h. Bacterial membranes were prepared as described in the same publication (Riga et al., 2015), diluted in $1 \times$ TSE buffer (0.1 M Tris acetate, pH 7.6, 0.5 M sucrose, 0.5 mM EDTA) and stored at -80 °C.

The CYP content was measured in reduced samples using Carbon monoxide (CO-difference spectra with a Cary double beam spectrophotometer (Agilent, USA). The activity of CPR was assessed by monitoring cytochrome *c* NADPH-dependent reduction assays at 550 nm using a SpectraMax-M2 multimode microplate reader (Molecular Devices, Berkshire, UK). Total protein concentration was determined by Bradford's assay (Bradford, 1976) at 595 nm, using bovine serum albumin standards and the same SpectraMax-M2 multimode microplate reader.

2.7. Activity of recombinant CYP against fluorescent model substrates

The activity of recombinant CYP was assessed using four fluorescent model substrates: 7-ethoxy-coumarin (7-EC), 7-ethoxy-4-trifluoromethyl coumarin (7-EFC), 7-ethoxy-4-methylcoumarin (7-EMC), and Dibenzyl fluorescein (DEF). Assays were conducted in black, flat-bottomed 96-well plates with each reaction containing 20 μ g of total protein per well, 1 mM NADPH, and 50 μ M of each substrate in 0.1 M Na/K-phosphate buffer (pH 7.6). Each data point was tested in quadruplicate, with control reactions consisting of CYPs incubated without NADPH and wells containing only buffer solution. Reactions were incubated at 30 °C for 30 min. For 7-EMC and DEF substrates, reactions were terminated by adding 100 μ L of stop solution (50 % DMSO and 0.05 M Tris/HCl, pH 10) prior to measurement. To prevent interference from NADPH fluorescence in 7-EC and 7-EFC reactions, 5 mM glutathione oxidized, and 0.2 units of glutathione reductase were added, and reactions were also terminated with the stop solution. Data were recorded using a SpectraMax-M2 multimode microplate reader (Molecular Devices, Berkshire, UK) at appropriate excitation/emission wavelengths for each substrate (7-EC at 390–465 nm, 7-EFC at 410–510 nm, 7-EMC at 355–460 nm, and DEF at 480–530 nm). Relative fluorescent units were converted to pmol of fluorescent products using standard curves generated with 7-HFC (7-hydroxy-4-(trifluoromethyl) coumarin), 7-HC (7-hydroxy-coumarin), 7-HMC (7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin), and F (fluorescein) for 7-EC, 7-EFC, 7-EMC, and DEF, respectively. A graph illustrating the substrate specificity of the recombinant CYP3002B2 was generated using GraphPad Prism v.8.0.2 (Graphpad Software, Boston, MA, USA).

2.8. HPLC analysis of acaricide metabolism

The metabolism of amitraz and flumethrin by CYP3002B2 was tested

using incubation assays followed by HPLC analysis to assess pesticide depletion and metabolite detection. Stock solutions of the pesticides were prepared in acetonitrile. Standard reactions included a final concentration of 25 μM for each pesticide and two CYP concentrations (0.25 μM for amitraz and 0.5 μM for flumethrin) in 100 μL Tris-HCl buffer (0.2 M, pH 7.4) with 0.25 mM MgCl_2 , and a final organic solvent concentration of 2.5 % (v/v). Incubations were conducted with and without an NADPH generating system comprising 1 mM glucose-6-phosphate, 0.1 mM NADP⁺, and 1 unit/mL glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PDH). The reactions were incubated at 30 °C, 1250 rpm, in an orbital shaker (Thermomixer Comfort, Eppendorf, Germany) and terminated at 0 and 2-h intervals using 100 μL acetonitrile, followed by an additional 30 min of stirring. The samples were then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min, and 100 μL of the supernatant was transferred to HPLC vials for reverse-phase HPLC analysis. The pesticides were separated on a 5 μm C18 (250 mm \times 4.5 mm) reverse-phase analytical column (Fortis 300 Technologies, UK). The optimal mobile phase for each pesticide is described in Suppl. Table S2. Reactions were monitored by absorbance changes at the specific optimal wavelength for each pesticide and quantified through peak integration (Chromeleon, Dionex). Each reaction was performed in triplicate and compared to a negative control without the NADPH regenerating system to calculate substrate depletion.

2.9. Analysis of acaricide metabolites by LC-MS

The activity of CYP3002B2 with amitraz and flumethrin, either with or without an NADPH generating system, was further investigated using a high-resolution HPLC-MS/MS system. Sample volumes of 1 μL and 10 μL were injected for amitraz and flumethrin respectively, using an Ultimate 3000 Autosampler (Thermo Scientific, USA). Chromatographic separation was performed using the Ultimate 3000 HPLC system (Thermo Scientific, USA) equipped with a 3 μm C18 (100 \times 2.1 mm) reverse-phase analytical column (Fortis Technologies, UK). The reactions were analyzed using an isocratic mobile phase of 85 % acetonitrile and 15 % H_2O , flowing at 0.2 mL/min for 12 min. Detection employed an electrospray ionization (ESI) Q Exactive Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA), operating in positive ion mode for amitraz and in negative ion mode for flumethrin. Mass spectrometry utilized full scan/extracted ion monitoring for each pesticide, with parallel reaction monitoring (PRM) specifically for amitraz. Control and data analysis were conducted using Xcalibur (v.4.0) software (Thermo Scientific, USA). Optimal spectrometer parameters included a spray voltage of 4000 V for amitraz and 3500 V for flumethrin, sheath gas pressure set at 20 arbitrary units, auxiliary gas pressure at 25 arbitrary units, and ion transfer capillary temperature maintained at 350 °C. For parallel reaction monitoring of amitraz, collision-induced dissociation at 20 eV was applied, utilizing high purity nitrogen for sheath/auxiliary and collision gases.

3. Results

3.1. Identification of amitraz and flumethrin resistance phenotype

The IL-R population, collected from Modiin, Israel, a region with a history of extensive acaricide applications, exhibited resistance to both amitraz and flumethrin in diagnostic bioassays (amitraz: 20 mg/L; flumethrin: 1 mg/L). Mortality rates in the IL-R population were 35.0 % for amitraz and 39.5 % for flumethrin, compared to >90 % mortality observed in both the IL-L and ATH-S populations (Table 1).

3.2. Target site resistance mutations present at low frequencies

Several *V. destructor* mites were genotyped using established TaqMan assays for target-site mutations, and transcriptomic analyses to investigate additional non-synonymous mutations also. The F290L putative

Table 1

Mortality rates of ATH—S, IL-L and IL-R populations tested with amitraz and flumethrin at diagnostic doses.

Population	n*	Amitraz Mortality [†] (% \pm SE)	n*	Flumethrin Mortality [†] (% \pm SE)
ATH-S	70	98.6 \pm 1.42	70	98.6 \pm 1.42
IL-L	40	90.0 \pm 4.37	41	90.2 \pm 5.30
IL-R	40	35.0 \pm 4.88	43	39.5 \pm 7.10

* Number of mites tested.

[†] Percentage mortality at diagnostic doses (%) \pm Standard Error (SE).

amitraz resistance mutation in the *Oct β 2R* gene was found at low frequency (8.6 %) exclusively in IL-R individuals, but none of the remaining amitraz resistance mutations that have been reported in the literature (i.e., N87S, Y215H and Y337F) were found in any of the *V. destructor* samples analyzed (Table 2). The pyrethroid resistance mutation L925V was found at low frequencies in the IL-R and the IL-L populations (13.6 % and 28.6 %, respectively) (Table 2). Collectively, these findings suggest that target-site resistance mechanisms have only a minimal association with the resistance phenotype in this population.

3.3. The overexpression of CYP3002B2 and cuticular protein genes is associated with resistance

Next, we carried out a transcriptomic analysis to identify genes potentially involved in the resistance phenotype. The transcriptomic profile of the resistant IL-R population was compared with both the IL-L and ATH-S populations. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) showed that the replicates of the three populations are clearly separated from each other.

Subsequently, we performed a DE analysis using the following cut-offs: $\log_2|\text{FC}| > 1$, p -value $< 1e^{-3}$, FDR < 0.05 (Suppl. Table S3). The analysis identified 163 up-regulated and 26 down-regulated genes in IL-R compared to ATH—S. In the comparison between IL-R and IL-L, 114 genes were up-regulated, and 5 genes were down-regulated.

Notably, 46 genes were commonly up-regulated in both comparisons, with no commonly down-regulated genes (Fig. 1 and Suppl. Table S3). Among those 46 commonly up-regulated genes, seven cuticular protein genes (e.g., cuticle proteins 14, 21, 63, 65, and cuticlin 1) were strongly overexpressed, with their fold change ranging from 10.22 to 35.75 in IL-R compared to ATH-S and from 2.67 to 81.59 in IL-R compared to IL-L (Fig. 1 and Suppl. Table S3). Notably, one CYP gene, *CYP3002B2* (LOC111244479), was found to be over-expressed 3-fold in IL-R compared to both IL-L (P -value = 3.39e-7) and ATH-S (P -value = 1.98e-13) (Fig. 1 and Suppl. Table S3). The remaining 38 commonly up-regulated genes included those coding for proteins such as zinc finger protein 512B, mucin 5 AC, cytochrome *b561*, peroxidase, collagen alpha 1(I) chain, protocadherin Fat 4, protein obstructor E, tubulin beta chain, as well as several uncharacterized proteins (Suppl. Table S3).

The downregulated transcripts identified in resistant *V. destructor* populations compared to susceptible ones include a range of genes associated with cellular processes, stress responses, and metabolic pathways (Table S3). No detoxification-related genes, such as CYPs, which might be associated with reduced proinsecticide activation-based resistance, were present in this dataset (Suppl. Table S3).

3.4. Functional expression of *V. destructor* CYP3002B2 in *E. coli*

Based on the observed expression pattern, CYP3002B2 was chosen for functional expression in *E. coli*. The *CYP3002B2* gene was co-expressed with *T. urticae* CPR in *E. coli* membranes, and all prepared membrane samples formed catalytically active monooxygenase complexes, as indicated by the recorded CO spectra (up to 6 nmol/L) (Suppl. Fig. S1). The CPR activity against cytochrome *c* was also verified, as shown in Suppl. Table S4.

Table 2
Target site resistance mutations analysis.

Acaricide	Amitraz				Flumethrin			
	Target-site mutation	N87S (<i>Octβ2R</i>)	Y215H (<i>Octβ2R</i>)	Y337F (<i>Octβ2R</i>)	F290L (<i>Octβ2R</i>)	L925V (<i>vgs</i>)	L925I (<i>vgs</i>)	L925M (<i>vgs</i>)
Population	% Mutation Frequency (hetero/homo), N of alleles							
IL-R	0.0 % (0/0), N = 82	0.0 % (0/0), N = 82	0.0 % N = 30	8.6 % N = 30	13.6 % (0/3), N = 44	0.0 % (0/0), N = 44	0.0 % (0/0), N = 44	0.0 % (0/0), N = 44
IL-L	0.0 % (0/0), N = 84	0.0 % (0/0), N = 84	0.0 % N = 20	0.0 % N = 20	28.6 % (0/4), N = 28	0.0 % (0/0), N = 28	0.0 % (0/0), N = 28	0.0 % (0/0), N = 28
ATH-S	0.0 % (0/0), N = 20	0.0 % (0/0), N = 20	0.0 % N = 20	0.0 % N = 20	0.0 % (0/0), N = 20	0.0 % (0/0), N = 20	0.0 % (0/0), N = 20	0.0 % (0/0), N = 20

Fig. 1. Transcriptomic analysis of the *V. destructor* populations. **A.** Number of differentially expressed genes ($|\log_2[FC]| > 1$, P -value $< 1E-03$, FDR < 0.05) between IL-R (resistant), IL-L (susceptible) and ATH-S (susceptible). Upward arrows indicate over-expressed genes, whereas downward arrows represent under-expressed genes in ILR compared to IL-L and ATH-S. **B.** Functional classification of the 46 commonly up-regulated genes in the two comparisons, IL-R vs ATH-S and IL-R vs IL-L. **C.** Normalized expression levels (z-scores) for detoxification enzymes and cuticular proteins.

We evaluated the metabolic efficiency of the recombinant CYP3002B2 using a range of fluorescent model substrates. CYP3002B2 exhibited low catalytic activity with the coumarin substrates 7-EMC (4.50 ± 0.14 pmol/min/mg) and 7-EC (4.04 ± 0.27 pmol/min/mg), very low catalytic activity with DEF (0.67 ± 0.05 pmol/min/mg), and no detectable activity with 7-EFC (Suppl. Table S5).

3.5. CYP3002B2 is capable of metabolizing acaricides

The ability of recombinant CYP3002B2 expressed in *E. coli* membranes to metabolize acaricides was tested against amitraz and flumethrin (Suppl. Table S6). Incubation of the CYP3002B2 complex with amitraz for 15 min resulted in a 16 % NADPH-dependent depletion of amitraz (eluting at 6.15 min) and the simultaneous formation of an

unidentified metabolite (M1, eluting at 2.55 min), compared to the control reaction without NADPH (Fig. 2A). LC-MS and MS/MS analysis of the reaction mixtures did not show the formation of the known toxic metabolites of amitraz, such as DMPF (N-Methyl-N'-(2,4-xylyl) formamide), DMF (2,4 dimethylformamide), or DMA (2,4 dimethylaniline), but confirmed the presence of hydroxylated amitraz as the major detectable metabolite, M1 (Fig. 2B). The mass spectrum, in positive ion mode, of the amitraz metabolite M1 exhibited a molecular ion peak at $m/z [M + H]^+ = 310.1906$, which was 15.99 Da higher than the corresponding peak of the parent compound at $m/z [M + H]^+ = 294.1959$. The +15.99 Da corresponds to the inclusion of an additional oxygen atom in the molecule, indicating hydroxylation. Several possible hydroxylation sites were suggested by the Biotransformer (v.3.0) theoretical tool (Fig. 2C). The MS/MS spectra fragmentation patterns for

Fig. 2. CYP3002B2 is active towards the acaricide amitraz. **A.** HPLC extracted ion chromatograms obtained using high resolution full scan MS show that CYP3002B2 causes a NADPH-dependent transformation of amitraz (eluting at 6.15 min) to a metabolite M1 (eluting 1371 at 2.55 min). **B.** Accurate mass spectra obtained using HPLC - electrospray ionization. Upper panel: High-resolution accurate mass of protonated amitraz at m/z 294.1959. Lower panel: High-resolution accurate mass of the protonated amitraz metabolite M1 at m/z 310.1906. Shown with their assigned elemental composition and corresponding mass accuracy. **C.** Possible structures of the hydroxylated metabolite of amitraz, with several possible hydroxylation sites according to the Bio 1376 Transformer 3.0 tool.

amitraz and its metabolite showed a consistent 15.99 Da increase in the product ions of the M1 metabolite (data not shown). This suggests that hydroxylation is the likely mechanism catalyzed by CYP3002B2, even though the exact structure of the hydroxylated amitraz metabolite could not be determined.

The HPLC-UV analysis of the reaction mixtures containing the CYP3002B2 complex (final concentration 0.5 μ M) with flumethrin, after 2-h of incubation, indicated a 16.5 % NADPH-dependent decrease in flumethrin (eluting at 8.33 min) and the concurrent appearance of an unidentified metabolite (M1, eluting at 7.36 min), in contrast to the control reactions lacking NADPH which did not show a reduction in flumethrin or the M1 metabolite (Fig. 3). LC-MS analysis of these reaction mixtures was not able to identify or characterize the unknown metabolite, potentially due to its degradation upon introduction into the ESI source.

In conclusion CYP3002B2 was able to metabolize both amitraz and flumethrin. The dominant product of amitraz metabolism was a hydroxylated, likely non active form, of the insecticide, but not DFMP (the major active metabolite) or any of the known activated metabolites.

4. Discussion

We identified and analyzed amitraz and pyrethroid resistance in a *V. destructor* population from Israel. First, we examined the association of known target-site resistance mechanisms with the phenotype. Only one putative amitraz resistance mutation (F290L in *Oct2R* gene) was identified exclusively in the resistant population, albeit at a very low frequency (8.6 %). This mutation has been previously identified and associated with amitraz resistance in *V. destructor* populations from Spain (Hernández-Rodríguez et al., 2024), however, its role in resistance has not yet been functionally validated. The pyrethroid resistance mutation L925V in the *vgsc* gene was detected at low frequencies in both the IL-L and IL-R *V. destructor* populations. This mutation, previously

reported in multiple European *V. destructor* populations (Erdem et al., 2024), has been shown to confer low-level resistance to flumethrin, even at near fixation frequencies (Vlogiannitis et al., 2021a).

Subsequently, by using transcriptomic analysis to compare gene expression levels in the resistant population (IL-R) versus two susceptible field populations (IL-L and ATH-S), we identified several cuticle genes, as well as *CYP3002B2*, to be overexpressed in the resistant population.

The overexpression of cuticular protein genes in the resistant *V. destructor* population was particularly striking, with several genes being overexpressed many times relative to both susceptible populations. The overexpression of cuticular protein genes has been associated with reduced insecticide penetration, which may delay the access of acaricides to their target sites and slow the rate of xenobiotic absorption, providing detoxification enzymes more time to metabolize the compounds (Balabanidou et al., 2018; Lilly et al., 2016). Notably, these modifications could also contribute to cross-resistance, potentially resulting in broad-spectrum resistance phenotypes, as observed here with amitraz and flumethrin.

The *CYP3002B2* gene was identified as a strong candidate for functional validation. It was significantly upregulated in the resistant IL-R population compared to both susceptible populations. Furthermore, phylogenetic analysis of *V. destructor* CYPs reveals that *CYP3002B2* clusters within the CYP2 clan, the same group as the CYP392 family in *T. urticae*, which has been largely associated with pesticide metabolism and resistance in mites (De Rouck et al., 2023), although this possible association would require functional confirmation.

Thus, we proceeded with the functional characterization of this gene, aiming to investigate its possible role in resistance. The recombinant CYP3002B2 was successfully expressed and shown to metabolize amitraz into a likely non-toxic hydroxylated metabolite, without producing any of the known activated/toxic metabolites associated with amitraz, namely DMPF (N-Methyl-N'-(2,4-xylyl) formamidine), DMF (2,4

Fig. 3. Metabolism of flumethrin by CYP3002B2. **A.** HPLC chromatogram of control reactions in the absence of NADPH regenerating system, showed no change after 2 h incubation in the initial flumethrin compound (eluting at 8,3 min). **B.** HPLC chromatogram showing 16,5 % NADPH-dependent flumethrin depletion (eluting at 8,3 min) and the parallel formation of one metabolite, the metabolite M1 (eluting at 7,3 min).

dimethylformamide) and DMA (2,4 dimethylaniline) (Cai et al., 2023; Giorgini et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2021; Kita et al., 2017; Schuntner and Thompson, 1978). Notably, CYP392A16 has been shown to confer metabolic resistance against amitraz in *T. urticae* by metabolizing amitraz to a hydroxylated metabolite (Vandenhoe et al., 2024).

The *V. destructor* CYP3002B2 protein was also capable of detoxifying flumethrin, an acaricide belonging to the distinct chemical class of pyrethroids. Therefore, its elevated expression levels associate CYP3002B2 with detoxification-based cross-resistance against acaricides with differing modes of action, which would be a major concern for resistance management. Similarly, CYP392A16 in *T. urticae* has been shown to detoxify multiple acaricides operating with different modes of action, including pyflubumide, abamectin, and amitraz (Fotoukiki et al., 2021; Riga et al., 2014; Tsakireli et al., 2024; Vandenhoe et al., 2024). In the study of (Tsakireli et al., 2024) several *T. urticae* CYP enzymes, including CYP392A11, CYP392A16, CYP392D2, and CYP392D8, which exhibit the ability to metabolize a wide variety of acaricides have been identified. Additional insect CYP enzymes have been reported to possess broad catalytic ranges, playing crucial roles in metabolizing a wide range of chemical classes (Katsavou et al., 2022; Nauen et al., 2022).

The exact contribution of CYP3002B2 to the intensity of the resistance phenotype in vivo, remains to be elucidated via RNAi or CRISPR-Cas9 knock out approaches in *V. destructor*, an experiment that could not be included in our study due to limited access to the live biological

material available for analysis (field resistant populations).

Nevertheless, the identification of CYP-based functionally validated metabolic resistance biomarkers enables monitoring of this type of metabolic resistance. Such efforts support pest control programs by providing end-users with accurate guidance on appropriate application strategies while also offering valuable insights into the origin and geographical spread of this resistance mechanism in *V. destructor*. The co-occurrence of this resistance mechanism with target-site resistance mutations—and potentially other factors, such as altered cuticle permeability—is concerning, as resistance at the operational level and subsequent control failures often result from the combined effects of multiple mechanisms (Lester, 2023; Mitton et al., 2022). The combination of the available diagnostics, with emphasis on functionally validated biomarkers, along with complementary bioassays, should be used to support evidence-based and rational use of acaricides, enabling effective resistance management strategies for the control of *V. destructor*.

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Konstantinos Mavridis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Dimitra Tsakireli:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Spyridon Vlogiannitis:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jason Charamis:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Inga Siden-Kiamos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis. **Angelina Fathia Osabutey:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Victoria Soroker:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Investigation. **John Vontas:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2025.106364>.

Data availability

The raw Illumina sequencing reads are deposited in Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under BioProject PRJNA1107372.

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